

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

DECHLORINATION OF A REAL PLASTIC WASTE PYROLYSIS OIL BY ADSORPTION WITH ZEOLITES

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Table S1. Distillation curve of the products of pyrolysis oils after the dechlorination process at different temperatures (ASTM D-2887 standard procedure).

Adsorption temperature (°C)	Raw	30	60	90	120	150	180
Initial boiling point (wt%)	38.1	34.8	33.6	33.6	33.6	38.3	37.9
1 wt%	39.9	37.0	35.2	35.3	35.3	39.9	39.6
2 wt%	58.3	60.9	53.5	53.5	53.4	57.7	56.8
3 wt%	64.2	62.1	59.5	59.5	59.3	63.8	62.6
4 wt%	67.2	65.3	61.0	61.0	61.0	65.3	65.3
5 wt%	69.5	70.1	64.2	64.2	64.2	68.7	67.7
6 wt%	79.3	77.6	75.9	75.5	75.6	79.1	78.2
7 wt%	86.1	89.9	78.8	78.1	78.2	84.8	83.8
8 wt%	93.1	91.1	90.5	90.5	90.4	93.1	92.4
9 wt%	96.2	94.2	92.6	92.0	92.1	96.0	95.3
10 wt%	97.1	95.3	94.7	94.7	94.7	97.1	96.6
20 wt%	136.3	133.4	133.4	133.4	133.3	136.4	134.7
50 wt%	248.3	245.3	243.0	242.5	242.3	247.8	242.9
90 wt%	367.4	366.9	367.2	367.3	367.2	367.6	367.0
Final boiling point (wt%)	433.5	428.7	428.3	428.6	428.9	434.5	428.8

Fig. S1. FT-IR/Pyridine spectra of both fresh and regenerated 13X zeolites after desorption at 150 °C.